

PSYCHOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOLCHILDREN

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Abstract: In this article, the nature of emotional intelligence of elementary school students is studied, the psychological features of the formation of emotional intelligence of students are studied.

Key words: Personality, emotional intelligence, information and communication technology, pedagogical activity, mental ability.

Introduction:

The reforms carried out in all spheres of our independent Uzbekistan raised the human factor to a higher level than ever before, and directly connected its strength, perception, potential, psychological and spiritual perfection with progress, civilization and development. Because of this, the problem of each person's perfection, self-knowledge, and understanding of others has become more urgent than ever.

As the sages of the East said in the Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Supreme Assembly, "*The greatest wealth is intelligence and knowledge, the greatest inheritance is a good education, and the greatest poverty is ignorance!*" For this reason, they emphasized that for all of us, mastering modern knowledge, becoming the owner of true enlightenment and high culture should become a continuous vital need¹.

It is noted that the student's readiness for the educational process depends on his personal-mental maturity, personal qualities, intellectual capabilities and social-psychological factors. It can be seen from this that interpersonal relations, mutual respect, empathy, which directly compete with the level of intelligence characterizing the mental abilities and understanding of the student, which play an important role in the formation of social qualities of a person, can read the experiences of other people, social intelligence that can understand trust and feelings. In many cases, the defects and deficiencies encountered in the student's activity during education are the result of the lack of social intelligence.

Therefore, researching the issue of the influence of social intelligence on the effectiveness of the student's activity in the modern educational process is the reason for a new topic of psychological research. It can be said with confidence that this was a logical continuation of the socially oriented state policy, which, from the first days of our independence, made raising a physically healthy and intellectually mature generation a priority. First of all, a healthy child is the fruit of a healthy and harmonious family.

¹ Ibragimov, B. (2023). Types And Importance Of Innovative Technologies In Education. Молодые ученые, 1(20), 96-98.

Noble qualities such as respect for elders, honor for children, humanity, kindness, loyalty to one's country and people are formed in the family environment. Also, one of the important issues facing world pedagogy and education today is the search for ways and means of forming not only educated, but also creative thinking, independent thinking person.

It is known that the idea of forming an independent thinker, intellectually mature, mentally fresh, intellectually complete person started from the time of the emergence of mankind, and it has been gradually developing during these periods. Concepts related to the upbringing of an independent thinker and a creative person are widely interpreted even today.

The idea of the student's freedom and his intellectual potential is one of the main ones in the fulfillment of this task. Already, a free person, a free people, is able to actively act in the process of creativity, prosperity, humanitarianism, creativity, science, culture and modern production and achieve the intended goals. At the present time, the sharp changes in the development of society impose qualitatively new and relatively complex tasks, in which the level of development of a person's intellect, the regulator of his mental capabilities, and moral aspects are of particular importance. One of the main characteristics of the period of personality formation is the rapid realization of social maturity.

Such maturity requires a person to acquire the necessary mental abilities, various roles to be performed in life and work. Mental maturity is especially important. Researching the nature of the social intelligence of schoolchildren, scientifically in-depth analysis is the demand of today, it is important to study in depth the methods of determining the social intelligence and analyze the characteristics of its dynamics in the upbringing of a mature generation, increasing its intellectual potential and professional formation. Raising today's youth so that they are not only physically strong, but also spiritually rich, meet the demands of the new era, and think clearly in the process of communication is one of the urgent problems of today.

The fate of the reforms implemented in our republic today depends on the moral image and personal integrity of the youth. The implementation of these tasks requires the full inculcation of democratic principles in human relations. In the process of liberating the society, it is necessary not only to create opportunities and conditions for the manifestation of the abilities and talents of a person in all aspects, but also to fully manifest the spiritual, spiritual and intellectual potential of a person. The issue of intellect has been studied for many years.

F. Galton (1822-1911) in his work "Heredity of Talent" considered that there is a correlation between physical and mental abilities and gave importance to heredity as a decisive factor, while J. Locke defined ability L.S. Vygotsky², who studied learning as a result, put forward the socio-historical aspect of the development of mental abilities and put forward the idea that the acquisition of knowledge is a process of participation in the culture created in the historical development of mankind. According to B.G.Ananev, abilities are not only the mastering of social experiences, but also thoughts and knowledge about the active activity of an individual and his psychological aspect, his relationship with a person. B. M. Teplov put forward the theory of musical talent, and he understands the success of musical activity as depending on a qualitatively specific combination of abilities. He studied the emotional

² Выготский Л.С. Мышление и речь. - 5-е изд., испр. - М.: Лабиринт, 1999. - с.

response to music as a key indicator. Scientific research conducted by N.S. Leytes on the issue of mental ability and talent is of particular importance. He considers the general mental abilities, which include the qualities of the mind, to be the main factor describing a person's theoretical knowledge and abilities in mental activity.

In addition, the problem of intelligence was widely studied by A.N. Leontev, P.YA. Galperin, V.A. Krutesky, A.M. Matyushkin and others, who conducted scientific research on intelligence and its composition and development³. Doctor of Psychological Sciences, Professor E.G. Goziev and other scientists have shed light on the specific aspects of the age of intellect in their scientific works. B.R. Kadirov explained in detail the definitions given to him in the naming of abilities and psychological characteristics close to him in the Uzbek language.

A.F.Azimova developed methods for determining the mental ability of students. B.R.Kodirov explained in detail the names of the abilities used in the Uzbek language and psychological characteristics close to it, as well as the definitions given to them. But the selection of talented young people and the organization of their further education have been studied very little. Talented psychologist B.R. Kadyrov (doctor of psychology, professor) dedicated his creative activity to the study of talented young people.

He studied the individual characteristics of youth in the field of differential psychology. Brain mechanisms of activity directions, abilities and primary abilities of students with social value in young people were studied. The neurophysiological aspects of students' choice of one or another direction of social activity were studied using electroencephalographic methods. The obtained data proved that there are alternative neurophysiological features in the brain activity that ensure the choice of profession, inclination to profession and types of abilities. A complex of mental tests was formed.

Currently, in our educational system, special demands are placed on the development of students' intelligence and creativity. One of the main goals of creating schools of creativity and presidential schools in our country is the development of creativity. In accordance with this demand and goal, special attention should be paid to the development of creativity development methods and technologies in psychology and pedagogy.

Conclusion:

But at the moment, there is no desire to quickly and comprehensively research this issue in the activities of our psychologists and pedagogues. If we take a look at the conclusions available in the world psychology science on the formation and development of creativity, first of all, it is known that creativity is formed and developed in the same way. and development is neglected. In our opinion, this situation is probably due to the lack of psychologists who can perform this task. There is a phenomenon that is a constant companion of creativity. This is a phenomenon called inspiration. If we can solve the problem of inspiring students in the process of forming creativity in them, we would have reached half of the goal set before us.

³ Ананьев Б. Г. Соотношение способностей и одаренности. В сб.: «Проблемы способностей», под ред.

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